

Potato microbial community library preparation

Preparing 16S and ITS DNA gene amplification for the Illumina MiSeq System

This document contains protocols that explain step by step the phases that one needs to go through to get from a freeze-dried potato sample to a 16S/ITS library suitable for Illumina sequencing.

Authors:

Yang Song (Postdoctoral researcher Utrecht University), Peter de Rooij (Technician Utrecht University), Casper Jongekrijg (Master student Environmental Biology), Ellen Manders (Master student Bio-inspired Innovation), Roeland Berendsen (Researcher Utrecht University)

Part 1: Processing Freeze-dried Samples

This part will guide you through the process of grinding freeze-dried potato samples to a fine powder. There are 2 main steps for this processing: The cleaning of the beads and the grinding process itself. It is important that the beads are cleaned and dried properly before use to prevent contamination between samples. Grinding the samples makes it easier to extract DNA from it later.

1.1 Cleaning

Materials

- 50 ml tubes
- MQ water
- 70% Ethanol
- Filter net
- Glas for waste water
- Large petri dishes
- Parafilm
- 5/6 mm metal beads

Methods

1. Sort out the different sizes of the metal beads (5/6 mm) and put each size in its own 50 ml tube.
2. Don't fill the tubes with too many beads. Try to keep it at half the volume of the tube.
3. Fill this tube with MQ water. Fill the tube to roughly 40 ml max. This makes it possible to shake the content of the tube more intense.
4. Shake the tube thoroughly for 30 seconds.
5. Place a filter net on top of the tube. The beads should not be able to pass through. Turn the tube upside down above a waste glass. All the wash-off will flow out of the tube while the beads stay inside.
6. Fill the tube again with water and repeat step 4 and 5.
7. Take a new clean 50 ml tube and transfer the beads to this new tube.
8. From this point on, all work is done in a flow cabinet to keep the beads sterile.
9. Fill the tube with 70% Ethanol to max 40 ml.
10. Repeat 4 and 5
11. Repeat step 9, 4, and 5
12. Since the clean beads will be used to grind freeze-dried samples, it is important that they are completely dry. Take some large petri dishes and put the clean beads from the tube to the plates. By putting them on a large clean surface, the ethanol can evaporate freely and more easily compared to when the beads remain stacked on top of each other in a tube.
13. Let the beads dry for as long as necessary (can take about two hours) check for yourself when they are dry. Keep the flow cabinet on while the beads dry!
14. Seal the petri dish with parafilm to keep them sterile outside the flow cabinet.

1.2 Grinding

Materials

- 50 ml tubes with freeze-dried sample

- Paint shaker machine
- custom-made box for shaking 50 ml tubes
- sterilized 5/6 mm metal beads from 1.1
- metal spoon
- 70% ethanol
- Tissues
- Strong magnet

Methods

1. Take a metal spoon and wash it with ethanol before use. Make sure it is dry before use.
2. Use the spoon to add 4 5/6mm bead from the sterile stock into each freeze-dried potato sample.
3. Shake the tubes for 9 minutes on max intensity in the paint shaker.
4. Check each tube to see if the sample is a fine powder. If not, this could be because the beads had too little space to move around in the tube. If this is the case, you can try to break the sample by shanking it by hand yourself first or try it with the sterilized spoon. After this, you can put it back into the machine for a second time.
5. Remove beads from the grinded samples using a magnet that is strong enough to attract the beads through the plastic of the tube. Avoid sample contamination by placing the magnet to the side of the tube to attract the beads. Subsequently remove the beads by swiping the magnet all the way up until the beads are out of the tube and bind directly to the magnet itself.

Part 2: DNA Isolation using KingFisher Flex

Materials

- PowerBead DNA Plates
- ClearMag Binding Solution
- ClearMag Beads
- RNase
- Plastic consumables of KingFisher Flex (5x KF 96 deep well plate, 1x KF 96 standard plate and 1x Tip comb)
- Homemade solutions (magnetic bead solution and solutions C1, C5 and C6)
- Qubit dsDNA BR (broad range) kit
- Qubit machine
- KingFisher Flex machine

We reverse engineered the powersoil kit (based on patent: US 7459,548 B2. Brolaski et al. 2008) and optimized a protocol using magnetic bead solution and solutions C1, C5 and C6 (C2, C3 and C4 proved redundant or deleterious of DNA yield from potato samples). The table below shows you how to prepare stock solutions and working solutions. The green numbers are relevant for preparing the stock solutions while the rest is relevant for the working solutions.

All stock solutions will be sterilized and kept sterile during storage. This means that you should only open them in a flow cabinet. Every stock solution will be sterilized by autoclaving **except from the guanidiniumisothiocyanate and SDS stocks**, which are heat sensitive and need to be filter sterilized.

For 1 reaction (uL)	For 100 reactions (ml)	Chemicals	Final concentration (mM)	Molecular weight (g/mol)	Stock concentration (mM)	Stock volume (ml)	Stock powder needed (g)	Mol needed	Stock volume for working solution (ml)
Magnetic bead solution									
750	75	NaH ₂ PO ₄	181	138	362	400	19,981	0,1448	37,5
		Guanidinium isothiocyanate	121	118,2	605	50	3,575	0,03025	15
		H ₂ O							22,5
Solution C1 (pH 10)									
60	6	NaCl	150	58,44	1500	200	17,532	0,3	0,6
		SDS	4%	288,4	20%	100	20	0,06938	1,2
		Tris	500	121,1	1000	100	12,11	0,1	3
		H ₂ O							1,2
Solution C5 (pH 7)									
1500	150	Tris	10	121,1					1,5
		NaCl	100	58,44					10
		EtOH	50%	na	99%				75,8
		H ₂ O							62,7
Solution C6 (pH 8)									
60	6	Tris	10	121,1					0,06

Methods

1. Prepare working solution (table above) from stock solutions and adjust them to appropriate pH.
2. Prepare two more solutions:
 - Add 400 uL RNase to 75 ml magnetic bead solution and vortex thoroughly (solution A)
 - Add 2 ml ClearMag beads to 45 ml ClearMag binding solution (solution B)
3. Weigh 75mg grinded powder sample into each well of the PowerBead DNA Plate.
4. Add 750 uL of solution A to every well with sample.
5. Add 60 uL C1 to every well with sample as well.
6. Place the plate in the tissuelyser on a programme with 20Hz for 10 minutes. Turn the plates for even shaking distribution and do one more time 20Hz for 10 minutes.
7. Take out the plate and measure its weight. Try to make another plate (preferably a used one or a 96 deep well KingFisher plate) with the same weight to balance for the centrifuging step.
8. Put the two plates in the centrifuge and spin for 6 minutes at 4500 g.
9. Take 400 uL of supernatant and transfer it to a deep well KingFisher plate.
10. Vortex and shake solution B thoroughly before use.
11. Put 470 uL of solution B in every well with supernatant.
12. Take 3 more deep well KingFisher plates and fill the required wells with 500 uL C5.
13. Take a standard KingFisher plate for the elution step. Add 100 uL C6 to every required well.
14. Set up the correct protocol on the KingFisher machine and follow the instructions on the screen to put the plates in the right order.
15. Measure DNA concentrations using dsDNA BR (broad range) kit on the Qubit following manufacturer's instructions.
16. Dilute all samples to a final concentration of 5 ng/μl in elution buffer C6 (pH 8).
17. Store DNA samples at -20°C

KingFisher programme details

Programme Title: KF_Flex_MoBio_PowerMag_Soil_DNA.bdz – BindIT 4.0

This programme is one of the standard ones from the KF company itself. No adjustments have been made except from some of the volumes specified below.

The image displays three screenshots of the KingFisher software interface, showing reagent and content information for different steps in the protocol.

Left Screenshot: Shows reagent information for a total volume of 870 uL (Maximum: 1000). The reagent list includes:

Reagent name	Volume [uL]	Color	Type
Supernatant	400	Red	Sample
Solution B	470	Grey	Reagent

 Content information shows a sequence of steps: Bind (Red), Wash 1 (Purple), Wash 2 (Purple), Wash 3 (Purple), Elution (Green), and Tip (White).

Middle Screenshot: Shows reagent information for a total volume of 500 uL (Maximum: 1000). The reagent list includes:

Reagent name	Volume [uL]	Color	Type
C5	500	Purple	Reagent

 Content information shows a sequence of steps: Bind (Red), Wash 1 (Purple), Wash 2 (Purple), Wash 3 (Purple), Elution (Green), and Tip (White).

Right Screenshot: Shows reagent information for a total volume of 100 uL (Maximum: 200). The reagent list includes:

Reagent name	Volume [uL]	Color	Type
C6	100	Green	Reagent

 Content information shows a sequence of steps: Bind (Red), Wash 1 (Purple), Wash 2 (Purple), Wash 3 (Purple), Elution (Green), and Tip (White).

Part 3: Amplification of marker genes (1st PCR)

Now that the DNA is extracted from the potato compartment and normalized to 5 ng/ul, it is time to amplify the DNA of interest. For fungi we target the ITS2 region and for bacteria the 16S region. Both regions need their own primers as listed below and in the summary table of all the relevant primers. PCR for 16S is done separately from ITS2.

Materials

- KAPA hotstart ready mix
- Sterile MQ water
- Primers (Supplementary Table 1)

Primers for 16S

V3/V4 Fw primer 16S-B341F-ill (2 uM)
V3/V4 Rv primer 16S-B806R-ill (2 uM)
pPNA blocking primer (2,5 uM)
mPNA blocking primer (2,5 uM)

Primers for ITS

ITS2 Fw primer fITS7 primer (2 uM)
ITS2 Rv primer ITS4-Rev primer (2 uM)
cl1ITS2-F blocking primer (2 uM)
clITS2-R blocking primer (2 uM)

Methods

- 1) Defrost the samples in the 96-well plate (plate with 2.5 ul gDNA **5ng/ul**) on ice
- 2) Centrifuge the defrosted plate at 1000 g for 1 min at 20°C (RT)
- 3) Prepare a master mix with the following components where $\chi = \text{no. of samples} * 110\%$

	1 x in ul	χ x in ul
Rv primer	2.5	$\chi * 2.5$
Fw primer	2.5	$\chi * 2.5$
Rv blocking primer	2.5	$\chi * 2.5$
Fw blocking primer	2.5	$\chi * 2.5$
KAPA hotstart ready mix	12.5	$\chi * 12.5$
Per sample	22.5	

- 4) Add 22.5 ul of the master mix to each sample (use PCR strip and multi-channel pipette)

- 5) Set and run the thermal cycler for amplicon (1st) PCR for 16S/ITS amplification with blocking primers. Total volume is 25 ul.
- 6) 1st PCR programme:

1. 95 °C for 3 min
2. 95 °C for 30 sec
3. 75 °C for 10 sec (Note!: blocking step, **only apply for 16S**)
4. 55 °C for 30 sec
5. 72 °C for 30 sec
6. Go to 2 for (**24** times if 16S / **9** times if ITS)
7. 72 °C for 5 min
8. Forever 10 °C

Part 4: First PCR Clean-up

PCR clean-up is a necessary step in the process of library preparation. It makes sure that there are no DNA degrading substances like enzymes present in your samples which makes it possible to store it under safer conditions and over a longer period. For KingFisher-mediated PCR clean-up we use the same solutions that are used for the DNA isolation. KingFisher programme title: PCRclean-up-AMpure.

Materials

- 4x 96 deep well plate
- 1x KF 96 standard plate
- 1x Tip comb
- Multichannel pipet basins
- AMPure beads
- 96% ethanol
- Pipet boy
- Sterile MQ water

Methods

1. Bring AMPure beads on room temperature before use
2. Sample plate:
Take a KF deep well plate and fill it with 25 ul pcr product (so all PCR product we have). Add 20 ul AMP-pure beads to each well with pcr product.
3. Washing plates:
Take 2 KF deep well plates and fill each well with 200 ul 80% ethanol. 80% ethanol is prepared by putting 41,7 ml 96% ethanol and 8,4 ml H₂O in a 50 ml tube and shake it. This is more than enough to fill both plates.
4. Elution plate:
Take a KF standard plate and fill it with 30 ul C6 if it is the first clean up, but 15 ul if it is the second clean up. These are the only volumes that are different compared to the “Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation protocol”. This to make sure we have high concentrations of DNA.
5. Tip comb plate:
Make sure that you have a KF deep well plate with a tip comb as well.
6. Place the plates in the KingFisher in the right order according to the programme.
7. Wait for half an hour. Once the machine is finished, take out the elution plate and put in the -20 fridge for storage. The other plates can go to the plastic waste.

Some tips

- Make sure that the tip comb is straight and not bended in any way. If it is bended, the binding and releasing steps of the beads become less accurate.
- If you place the plates in the machine, make sure that well A1 is always in the top right corner.

SAFE STOPPING POINT

Part 5: Second PCR to incorporate indexing primers

The first PCR and clean-up are done now. Next will be the second PCR and second clean-up. The second PCR is also called index PCR because we use index primers. For the first PCR we used illumina primers. These primers have a specific sequence at the end that allows for index PCR. For index PCR we use 20 primers total. Those primers will be used to create 96 unique combinations. Every well gets its own combination of primers according to the schematic picture below. The index primers bind to the end of the illumina primer sequence from the first PCR to amplify the target DNA even more.

Materials

- Index primers (Supplementary Table 2)
- KAPA hotstart ready mix
- Sterile MQ water
- Microseal

Methods

- 1) Centrifuge the plate with 2.5 ul amplicon (1st) PCR product at 1000 g for 1 min at 20°C
- 2) Make master mix where $\chi = \text{no. of samples} * 110\%$

	1x in ul	χ x in ul
KAPA	12.5	$\chi * 12.5$
Sterile MQ	5.0	$\chi * 5.0$
Per sample	17.5	

- 3) Orient the index primers according to this picture (put the index primers working solutions in PCR strips for multi-channel pipette, spin down before use)

	701	702	703	704	705	706	707	708	709	710	711	712
501	A1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
502	B											
503	C											
504	D											
505	E											
506	F											
507	G											
508	H											

- 4) Add 2.5 ul of primers 701-712 to all rows
- 5) Add 2.5 ul of primers 501-508 to all columns
- 6) Check by eye if all wells are filled and have an equal volume

- 7) Add 17.5 ul of the master mix to each well (carefully avoid cross-contamination)
- 8) Gently pipette up and down 10x to mix
- 9) Cover the plate with microseal
- 10) Centrifuge 1000 g 1 min 20°C
- 11) Set and run the thermal cycler for index (2nd) PCR. Total volume is 25 ul.

1. 95 °C for 3 min
2. 95 °C for 30 sec
3. 55 °C for 30 sec
4. 72 °C for 30 sec
5. Go to 2 for (9 times if 16S / 24 times if ITS)
6. 72 °C for 5 min
7. Forever 10 °C

Part 6: Second PCR Clean-up

The 2nd clean-up is the same as the first clean-up. The only difference is the amount of elution buffer for the final step.

Materials

- 4x 96 deep well plate
- 1x KF 96 standard plate
- 1x Tip comb
- Multichannel pipet basins
- AMPure beads
- 96% ethanol
- Pipet boy
- Sterile H₂O

Methods

8. Bring AMPure beads on room temperature before use.
9. Sample plate:
Take a KF deep well plate and fill it with 25 ul pcr product (so all PCR product we have). Add 20 ul AMP-pure beads to each well with pcr product.
10. Washing plates:
Take 2 KF deep well plates and fill each well with 200 ul 80% ethanol. 80% ethanol is prepared by putting 41,7 ml 96% ethanol and 8,4 ml H₂O in a 50 ml tube and shake it. This is more than enough to fill both plates.
11. Elution plate:
Take a KF standard plate and fill it with 20 ul C6.
12. Tip comb plate:
Make sure that you have a KF deep well plate with a tip comb as well.
13. Place the plates in the KingFisher in the right order according to the programme.
14. Wait for half an hour. Once the machine is finished, take out the elution plate and put in the -20 fridge for storage. The other plates can go to the plastic waste.

Some tips

- Make sure that the tip comb is straight and not bended in any way. If it is bended, the binding and releasing steps of the beads become less accurate.
- If you place the plates in the machine, make sure that well A1 is always in the top right corner.

SAFE STOPPING POINT

If you do not plan to proceed to Library Quantification, Normalization, and Pooling, seal plate with adhesive seal and store it at -15 to -20 °C for up to a week.

Part 7: Agarose Gel Electrophoresis

Compare your sample band to the ladder shows how big the fragment is and if it corresponds with the length you expected based on the primers you used. For our experiment we expect 650 base pairs.

Materials

- Agarose
- TBE (Tris-Borate-EDTA) buffer
- Measuring glass
- Scale
- Microwave
- 1KB plus DNA ladder
- Plastic gel holder + combs
- (multichannel) pipet + tips
- Loading dye

Methods

1. Measure 50-200ml TBE buffer then mix with 1% of Agarose powder on a scale.
2. Place the mixture of TBE buffer and agarose mix in a microwave. Depending on the size of the gel you are preparing you will probably need between 1 to 4 minutes for your solution to be in the microwave. During this time, the agarose will dissolve. The liquid is ready when there are no transparent crystals of agarose floating in the TBE buffer anymore.
3. Cool the TBE-agarose mix to around 60 degree.
4. Add 1 droplet of Ethidium Bromide to the mixture for every 50 ml of TBE-agarose mix.
Be careful with Ethidium Bromide because it is highly mutagenic!
5. Pour the TBE-agarose mix into this plastic holder, place the combs in the right place and wait for the gel to get solid.
6. Mix 3 ul Orange loading dye with 3 ul of cleaned 2nd PCR product
7. Use 5 ul of this 6 ul for loading samples in the gel
8. Use 8 ul DNA ladder in the gel

Your gel might look like this afterwards:

Part 8: Library Quantification, Normalization, and Pooling

Materials

- dsDNA BR kit (Qubit buffer, standard 1 and 2, fluorescent dye)
- 500 ul Qubit tubes
- Tube holder
- Marker to write on tubes
- Tris buffer
- Pipet+ tips
- Lobind Tube

Methods

9. Measure DNA concentrations using dsDNA BR (broad range) kit on the Qubit following manufacturer's instructions.
10. Calculate the DNA concentration in nM for each sample
11. Qubit gives an output in ng/ul. To normalize the libraries, the concentration in nM is needed for the samples. The calculation for ng/ul to nM is:
12. $\text{Qubit conc.} / (660 * X) * 10^6 = \text{conc. in nM}$
13. Where X is the average library size.
14. Dilute each sample to 4 nM using 10 mM Tris pH 8.5
15. Pool 5 ul of each normalized sample with unique indices (index primer combination) together in one Lobind Tube. Afterwards, there should be 5 ul from 96 samples ($5 * 96 = 480 \text{ul}$) with unique index primers in one tube if it is a full run.
16. Store libraries at $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and ready to submit to sequencing facility.

Supplementary Table1 primer list for 1st PCR

Sequence Name	5' Modification	Sequence
16S V3-V4	16S-B806R	GGACTACHVGGGTWTCTAAT
ITS2	fITS7	GTGARTCATCGAATCTTTG
ITS2	ITS4-Rev	TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC
16S V3-V4 illumina	16S-B341F-ill	TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGCCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG
16S V3-V4 illumina	16S-B806R-ill	GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGGACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC
ITS2 illumina	fITS7-ill	TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGGTGARTCATCGAATCTTTG
ITS2 illumina	ITS4-ill	GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGTCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC
blocking primers 16S Mito	mPNA	ggcaagtgttcttcgga
blocking primers 16S Plastid	pPNA	ggctcaaccctggacag
blocking primers ITS2	cl1ITS2-F	CGTCTGCCTGGGTGTCACAAATCGTCGTCC
blocking primers ITS2	clITS2-R	CCTGGTGTGCTATATGGACTTTGGGTCAT

Supplementary Table2 primer list for 2st PCR

Sequence Name	5' Modification	Sequence
S501	None	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC TAGATCGC TCGTCGGCAGCGTC
S502	None	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC CTCTCTAT TCGTCGGCAGCGTC
S503	None	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC TATCCTCT TCGTCGGCAGCGTC
S504	None	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC AGAGTAGA TCGTCGGCAGCGTC
S505	None	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC GTAAGGAG TCGTCGGCAGCGTC
S506	None	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC ACTGCATA TCGTCGGCAGCGTC
S507	None	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC AAGGAGTA TCGTCGGCAGCGTC
S508	None	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC CTAAGCCT TCGTCGGCAGCGTC
N701	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT TCGCCTTA GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N702	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT CTAGTACG GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N703	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT TTCTGCCT GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N704	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT GCTCAGGA GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N705	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT AGGAGTCC GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N706	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT CATGCCTA GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N707	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT GTAGAGAG GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N708	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT CCTCTCTG GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N709	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT AGCGTAGC GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N710	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT CAGCCTCG GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N711	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT TGCCTCTT GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG
N712	None	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT TCCTCTAC GTCTCGTGGGCTCGG